

Improving Human Action Recognition with Neuronal Competition in Spiking Neural Networks

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Abstract—This study presents an end-to-end spiking pipeline trained with semi-supervised STDP for human action recognition, comprising an unsupervised feature extractor and a supervised classifier. It shows that incorporating neuronal competition in the classifier improves class separation by promoting the learning of various spatio-temporal patterns per class.

I. INTRODUCTION

Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) are a promising alternative to traditional artificial neural networks for energy-efficient and spatio-temporal processing. These properties make SNNs well-suited for Human Action Recognition (HAR), which requires learning patterns across space and time. Prior work [1] showed effective unsupervised feature learning in 3D Convolutional SNNs (3DCSNNs) using Spike Timing-Dependent Plasticity (STDP). However, their method used a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classification, which is not compatible with neuromorphic systems.

In this study, we present a semi-supervised spiking pipeline based on STDP for HAR, replacing the SVM classifier with a spiking alternative that leverages supervised STDP and neuronal competition. Specifically, we consider a classification architecture based on Neuronal Competition Groups (NCGs) [3] and trained with Stabilized Supervised STDP (S2-STDP) [2]. This architecture has recently achieved state-of-the-art performance on image classification tasks in a similar semi-supervised setting [3]. However, its effectiveness in separating spatio-temporal features remains unclear. Our main contribution is to establish the applicability of NCGs in a spatio-temporal context.

II. METHODS

Our semi-supervised pipeline consists of two stages: a 3DCSNN trained with unsupervised STDP for feature extraction, and a classifier trained with supervised STDP for classification. Training is performed layer-wise.

a) Feature Extractor: The feature extractor, adapted from [1], comprises a 3D convolutional layer of integrate-and-fire neurons, followed by a sum-pooling layer. First, each video frame is preprocessed and encoded into spikes using latency coding. Then, the convolutional layer processes the spike-encoded video and performs STDP training to learn spatio-temporal features. Last, sum-pooling is applied to reduce spatial resolution, and the resulting spike counts are re-encoded using latency coding. Each output feature captures spatio-temporal information encoded as a single spike time; features are flattened and passed to the classifier.

b) Classifier: The classifier, adapted from [3], is a fully-connected layer of $N = C \times M$ integrate-and-fire output neurons, where C is the number of classes and M is the number of neurons per class. It is trained with S2-STDP, an error-modulated STDP with state-of-the-art performance. We compare two settings: (1) a baseline with $M = 1$; (2) a layer augmented with NCGs, where $M > 1$. NCGs map each class to a group of M neurons that employ intra-class winner-takes-all competition and supervised threshold adaptation. On image classification, this method enabled the learning of various class-specific patterns, greatly improving class separation without increasing the number of layers. We aim to validate their properties on spatio-temporal features.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We evaluate our pipeline on the KTH dataset [4], an HAR benchmark with 600 videos of 6 actions ($C = 6$). We use 10 frames per video. For each setting, the classifier’s hyperparameters were extensively tuned using a validation set derived from the training data to ensure optimal performance. Table I presents the test accuracy for each classifier.

TABLE I: Classification accuracy on the KTH dataset.

Classifier	M	Accuracy (%)
S2-STDP (baseline)	1	58.80
S2-STDP+NCGs	3	65.28
S2-STDP+NCGs	5	66.67
SVM [1]*	–	63.43

*3-layer 3DCSNN, 8-frame videos.

Incorporating NCGs significantly improves the accuracy of the classifier trained with S2-STDP, and outperforms the non-spiking SVM classifier. These results show the applicability of neuronal competition in enhancing class separation for spatio-temporal data. Future work could explore larger HAR datasets, investigate the nature of class-specific patterns learned by NCGs, and design competition mechanisms tailored for temporal processing.

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